

Geometry in Ancient Town-Plannings

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Abstract This work discusses a possible manner of using the geometry, based on right triangles, to determine the orientation of ancient town-plannings. Examples are given concerning some towns founded by Romans.

Keywords: Centuriation, Orientation of Roman colonies, Varatio.

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The Roman colonies were planned by means of a land survey method which is known as *limitation* or *centuriation*. [1]. This plan is characterized by a layout in the form of a square or rectangular grid, which is made by parallel and perpendicular roads, canals or dry-walls, which subdivided the settlement into *insulae*. The *insulae* were the house-blocks in the towns or the agricultural plots in the countryside. In some cases these plots were allocated to Roman army veterans [2].

Actually, the town-planning of Roman colonies was following the Hippodamian system with two main streets, the *cardo maximus* and the *decumanus maximus*, crossing at the centre of the city. The city was therefore made by four main districts, created by these streets. In [3], the Hippodamian Plan is defined as a city plan that looks like a gridiron, that is a frame of parallel lines, typically in two sets forming a grid. "An early example is Tell el-Amarna in Egypt, dating back to the fifteenth century BCE; Enkomi is a bit younger. The idea was introduced in the Greek world by Hippodamus of Miletus, who designed the new port of Athens, Piraeus, in the mid-fifth century BCE" [3]. Actually, Hippodamus probably was not the first Greek "to base a city on a gridiron plan". In fact, his hometown Miletus had a gridiron plan too. Consequently, "we must assume that 'Hippodamian Plan' is something of a misnomer" [3]. Examples of ancient cities having the Hippodamian plan are "Pella and Olynthus in Macedonia, Halicarnassus in Caria, Alexandria in Egypt, Apamea and Dura Europos in Syria, Seleucia in Babylonia, Acragas on Sicily, Priene in Ionia, Laodicea in Phrygia, Byllis in Illyria, and Taxila in the Punjab, and Emporiae in Catalonia. The Romans would use this design as well, using it when they expanded existing cities (e.g., Pompeii) and founded new cities (e.g., Augusta Emerita)" [3]. Of Dura Europos we discussed in [4].

Of course, the choice of the place of a town or colony was dictated by the local environment and the presence of rivers and roads. Then, the grid had to be orientated according to the chosen place of the foundation. Consequently it was necessary to decide the directions of the main streets: this was one of ancient surveyors' jobs. Usually, the operations made by the surveyor are described in the following manner. To subdivide the land, the surveyor first identified a central viewpoint, known by the Romans as *umbilicus agri* or *umbilicus soli*. He then took up his position there and, after assuming a specific orientation, defined the territory with the following names: *ultra*, the land he saw in front of him; *citra*, the land behind him; *dextera*, the land to his right; *sinistra*, the land to his left [5,6]. He then traced two road axes perpendicular to each other (the *decumanus maximus* and

the *cardo maximus*). After a grid of parallel and perpendicular roads were traced to subdivide the land into *insulae*. According to the Latin writer Frontinus [6], who was referring Varro, the Romans inherited the manner to subdivide the land from the Etruscan Doctrine. However, this was just an interpretation made by the ancient writer Varro, as explained in [1]. Actually, as previously told, the plan of Roman colonies was following the Hippodamian system.

We read in [6] that the *decumanus* runs from *oriens* to *occasus*, that is from the sunrise to the sunset. After these words, some scholars, such as Barthel [5], argued for an orientation of the *decumanus* towards the point of the horizon where the sun was rising, *secundum coelum*, but other scholars maintained that the orientation was just dictated by the local environment or by the main roads of the area, as stressed by Le Gall and Castagnoli [7,8]. In any case, to have the regular grids of the limitation matching the local environments (rivers, hills, mountains, main roads, longest axis of the local topography), that is *secundum naturam*, the Roman surveyors had to rotate the grids. To perform this task, the surveyors had some rules that we can find in the literature of the *Gromatici*, which are defined as *varatio* [9,10]. *Varatio* is also mentioned by Vitruvius [11]. In fact, geometry was required to plan and measure the new settlements.

According to [12], the term *varatio*, also written *uaratio*, refers to a process of oblique surveying. As told by [12], it has been shown by Anne Roth-Congès [13] that at least two approaches were employed; there was a *uaratio fluminis* [14], by means of which the distance of an inaccessible point could be calculated by the construction of right angled triangles, and there was a *uaratio in agris diuisis*, that the surveyors could make by means of lines “along the hypotenuse of right angled triangles defined in a rectangular coordinate system” [12]. This second *uaratio* is the one which is statistically analyzed in [12]. As stressed by John Peterson, when introducing his analysis, the variety of observed oblique relationships, is limited. The scoring function is giving ratios: 0:1,1:5, 1:4, 1:3, 1:2, 3:5, 2:3, 3:4, 1:1. For what concerns a possible orientation with a sighting by stars [15], Peterson considers it an approach “which does not seem very feasible, since it would have obliged surveyors to work at night”.

Besides the study of *varatio* concerning the Hadrian’s Wall and the Wetterau Limes [12], we can find the *varatio* considered for the orientation of the Roman towns in Spain [16]. In [17], the approach of [16] is considered with a specific aim. The authors of [16], that have studied the orientation of 81 Roman towns in the Iberian Peninsula having *varatio* angles with aspect ratios up to 12:12, “want to discern whether the orientations were astronomical, purely geometrical, or if geometry could have fostered astronomical aims by using selected and well-known angles to trace lines that fitted the desired astronomical purposes.” The work is, according to their words, “an attempt to shed more light to the issue of the orientation of Roman towns by combining two hypotheses that, in contrast to what it might seem, could be complementary but not contrary.”

Of course, also for the Roman towns in Italy and other countries, the study of their *varatio* is an interesting research. The reason of the research could be the same as for [17].

In [18], we have considered the case of Como and Verona. These two towns have a possible solstice orientation [19,20,21]. For what concerns Como, we know that it was around the 1st century BC that the territory became subject to Rome. In origin, the town was situated on the nearby hills. It was moved to the current location by Julius Caesar. The newly founded town, in 59 BC, was named *Novum Comum*. In the case of Verona, its territory became Roman about 300 BC. Verona became a Roman colony in 89 BC, and it was classified as a *municipium* in 49 BC.

Como and Verona have a town-planning based on a grid rotated of 36° and 37.5° , with respect to the East-West axis (Figure 1). Actually, the plan of the two towns is a chessboard as in the Figure 2. Then, if we use the East-West axis as the hypotenuse of a right triangle, the catheti have their lengths corresponding to the lengths of 3 and 4 *insulae*. Actually, we have that the rectangular triangle in the case of Como and Verona is that of the fundamental Pythagorean triple 3,4 and 5.

In the Figure 1, the two catheti give the directions of the decumanus and the cardo. The angle that the decumanus and the hypotenuse form is given by $\alpha = \arctan(3/4) = 36.87^\circ$. Therefore, the azimuth from true North, of the decumanus is $53,13^\circ$.

Figure 1.

Figure 2

Measuring by the maps the azimuths of decumani, we can tell, as discussed in [18], that the varatio of Como and Verona was based on ratio 3:4 of catheti.

The varatio of other ancient towns had been discussed in [22-26].

Now, as done in the literature concerning the varatio, let us consider the geometry which was necessary to measure distances and determine directions on the land. Let us consider the right triangle in the Figure 3.

Figure 3.

Once the orientation of the town-planning had been decided, the surveyor had to determine the direction of the local meridian line and of the East-West direction. This direction is coincident to

that of the hypotenuse AD of the right triangle. Actually, the surveyor had a frame of reference made by two axes, which were giving the directions of BC and AD . After fixing the unit u , to have the specific direction of the decumanus the surveyor had simply to measure on these axes x_2 and h . In this manner, the positions of points A and B were determined, having therefore AB as the decumanus and BD as the cardo. The lengths of AB and BD are $\xi u\sqrt{1+\xi^2}$ and $u\sqrt{1+\xi^2}$ respectively.

Actually, we can give the following cases of towns founded by Romans, as examples of the used geometry. For some of them, it is possible to determine ξ from the insulae which are yet visible in the modern towns, such as in the case of Como and Verona. In other cases, we determined it as the tangent of the azimuth of decumanus (α in the Figure 3). Let us note that the uncertainty, at least, is of 1.5 degree according to the measurements concerning Como and Verona.

Torino (Augusta Taurinorum):	$ratio=1:2$	$\xi=2$	$x_1=1$	$h=2$	$x_2=4$
Concordia Sagittaria:	$ratio=1:2$	$\xi=2$	$x_1=1$	$h=2$	$x_2=4$
Nicopolis in Old Epirus:	$ratio=1:3$	$\xi=3$	$x_1=1$	$h=3$	$x_2=9$
Trier (Augusta Treverorum):	$ratio=1:3$	$\xi=3$	$x_1=1$	$h=3$	$x_2=9$
Minturno:	$ratio=1:3$	$\xi=3$	$x_1=1$	$h=3$	$x_2=9$
Chester (Deva Victrix):	$ratio=1:4$	$\xi=4$	$x_1=1$	$h=4$	$x_2=16$
Aosta (Augusta Praetoria):	$ratio=2:5$	$\xi=5/2$	$x_1=2$	$h=5$	$x_2=12.5$
Winchester (Venta Belgarum):	$ratio=2:5$	$\xi=5/2$	$x_1=2$	$h=5$	$x_2=12.5$
Pavia (Ticinum):	$ratio=2:7$	$\xi=7/2$	$x_1=2$	$h=7$	$x_2=24.5$
Parma:	$ratio=2:7$	$\xi=7/2$	$x_1=2$	$h=7$	$x_2=24.5$
Bologna (Bononia):	$ratio=2:9$	$\xi=9/2$	$x_1=2$	$h=9$	$x_2=40.5$
Vicenza:	$ratio=7:12$	$\xi=12/7$	$x_1=7$	$h=12$	$x_2=20.5$
Verona:	$ratio=3:4$	$\xi=4/3$	$x_1=3$	$h=4$	$x_2=5.3$
Como:	$ratio=3:4$	$\xi=4/3$	$x_1=3$	$h=4$	$x_2=5.3$
Vienna (Vindobona):	$ratio=3:4$	$\xi=4/3$	$x_1=3$	$h=4$	$x_2=5.3$
Évora (Ebora Liberalitas Julia):	$ratio=3:5$	$\xi=5/3$	$x_1=3$	$h=5$	$x_2=8.3$
Ostia Antica:	$ratio=3:5$	$\xi=5/3$	$x_1=3$	$h=5$	$x_2=8.3$
Piacenza:	$ratio=5:6$	$\xi=6/5$	$x_1=5$	$h=6$	$x_2=7.4$
Autun (Augustodunum):	$ratio=5:8$	$\xi=8/5$	$x_1=5$	$h=8$	$x_2=12.8$
Venafro:	$ratio=5:8$	$\xi=8/5$	$x_1=5$	$h=8$	$x_2=12.8$
Alife:	$ratio=5:8$	$\xi=8/5$	$x_1=5$	$h=8$	$x_2=12.8$

As shown in [4], Dura Europos has the same geometry of Torino. For what concerns Ebora Liberalitas Julia, in [27] it is told that the orientation of its decumanus is according to the sunrise on summer solstice. Piacenza has the decumanus aligned along the southernmost azimuth of the moonrise [28]. The plan of Winchester, the Roman Venta Belgarum, is given in [29].

The results coming from the geometry, such as those given above, must be considered when an astronomical approach to the orientation of Roman towns is supposed. In particular, we can see that towns, at quite different latitudes, have the same geometry. Therefore, an astronomical orientation of a Roman town could be simply a mere coincidence because of the chosen geometry. For this reason, an astronomical determination of decumanus (or cardo) azimuth cannot be considered, a priori, as necessarily involved in the foundation of the town. It is a possibility, not a rule.

References

- [1] Sparavigna, A. C. (2020). *La Limitatio Romana: Alcune Definizioni*. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3717086>
- [2] Haverfield, F. (1913). *Ancient town - planning*, Oxford, The Clarendon Press, 1913, available at <http://www.gutenberg.org/files/14189/14189-h/14189-h.htm>
- [3] www.livius.org/articles/concept/hippodamian-plan/
- [4] Sparavigna, A. C. (2020). *The Geometry of Dura-Europos town-planning*. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3711688>
- [5] Barthel, W. (1911). *Römische Limitation in der Provinz Africa*, 1911, CXX, pp. 39-126. Carl Georgi Verlag, Bonn.
- [6] In the *Corpus Agrimensorum Romanorum*, which is the Roman book on land surveying collecting works by Siculus Flaccus, Frontinus, Aggenus Urbicus, Hyginus Gromaticus and other writers, we find the following (ex libro Frontini secundo): *Limitum prima origo, sicut Varro descripsit, a disciplina Etrusca; quod aruspices orbem terrarum in duas partes diuiserunt, dextram appellauerunt quae septentrioni subiaceret, sinistram quae ad meridianum terrae esset, ab oriente ad occasum, quod eo sol et luna spectaret, sicut quidam architecti delubra in occidentem recte spectare scripserunt. Aruspices altera linea ad septentrionem a meridiano diuiserunt terram, et a media ultra antica, citra postica nominauerunt.*
- [7] Castagnoli, F. (1958). *Le ricerche sui resti della centuriazione*. Storia e Letteratura. Roma 1958.
- [8] Le Gall, J. (1975). *Les romains et l'orientation solaire*. MEFRA 87-1975-1, p. 287-320.
- [9] Libertini, G. (2018). *Gromatici Veteres - Gli Antichi Agrimensori - Traduzione in italiano con commenti, figure, schemi e illustrazioni a cura di Giacinto Libertini e con presentazione di Gianluca Soricelli*. Istituto Di Studi Atellani, Frattamaggiore, Naples & Copernican Editions
- [10] B. Campbell, *The Writings of the Roman Land Surveyors. Introduction, Text, Translation and Commentary (Journal of Roman Studies Monograph 9)*. London: Society for the Promotion of Roman Studies, 2000.
- [11] M. Vitruvii Pollionis *De architectura libri decem. Cum notis, castigationibus & observationibus Guilielmi Philandri integris; Danielis Barbari excerptis, & Claudii Salmasii passim insertis*. Apud Ludovicum Elzevirium, Amstelodami, 1649.
- [12] Peterson, J. W. (2001). *Design and Performance of the Varatioscope*. BAR International Series, 931, 269-272.
- [13] Roth Congés, A. (1996). *Modalités pratiques d'implantation des cadastres romains: quelques aspects*. Mélanges de l'école française de Rome 108: 299-422.
- [14] Bouma, J. (1993). *Marcus Iunius Nypsus: Fluminis varatio, Limitis repositio: introduction, text, translation, and commentary (Vol. 77)*. Peter Lang Pub Inc. www.peterlang.com/view/title/39249

- [15] Margary, I. D. (1973). *Roman Roads in Britain* (Revised Edition). London: John Baker.
- [16] Orfila, M., Chávez, M^a E., & Sánchez, E. H. (2014). *Las estructuras ortogonales de nueva planta en época romana. De la varatio y sus variaciones*. Granada, ISBN: 978-84-338-56-9. Publisher: Universidad de Granada; Servicio de Publicaciones de la Universidad de la Laguna y la Universidad de Valladolid.
- [17] Rodríguez-Antón, A., Pons, M. O., González-García, A. C., & Aviles, J. B. (2019). The Uaratio and Its Possible Use in Roman Urban Planning to Obtain Astronomical Orientations. In *Archaeoastronomy in the Roman World* (pp. 103-120). Springer, Cham.
- [18] Sparavigna, A. C., & Marazzato, R. (2019). The Geometry in the Urban Layout of the Roman Como and Verona: The Same Solution to Different Problems (July 25, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3426608> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3426608>
- [19] Sparavigna, Amelia Carolina, Roman Towns Oriented to Sunrise and Sunset on Solstices (May 8, 2016). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2777118> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2777118>
- [20] Morandotti, L. (2011). Quel solstizio che disegnò il volto di Como. *Corriere di Como*.
- [21] Gaspani, A. (2009). Verona. Origini storiche e astronomiche. Edizioni della Vita Nova di Giovanni Perez.
- [22] Sparavigna, A. C. (2019). The Roman Towns and the geometry - Examples of Varatio. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3370498>
- [23] Sparavigna, A. C. (2019). The Geometry of the Roman Torino, that is to say the Varatio of Augusta Taurinorum. Zenodo. 2019, October 16. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3493368>
- [24] Sparavigna, A. C. (2019). Augusta Taurinorum, città di Vitruvio. Zenodo. 2019, October 21. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3515424>
- [25] Sparavigna, A. C. (2020). Aosta, la geometria e i venti di Vitruvio. Zenodo. 2020, January 3. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3597473>
- [26] Sparavigna, A. C. (2020). Notes on the orientation of the town-planning of Nicopolis, the capital of Old Epirus. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3727059>
- [27] Bertarione, S. V., & Magli, G. (2015). Augustus' Power from the Stars and the Foundation of Augusta Praetoria Salassorum, *Cambridge Archaeological Journal*, 25(1), 1 - 15.
- [28] Sparavigna, A. C. (2019). Piacenza e la Luna. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2650467>
- [29] Boerefijn, W. N. A. (2010). The foundation, planning and building of new towns in the 13th and 14th centuries in Europe: an architectural-historical research into urban form and its creation. University of Amsterdam. pure.uva.nl/ws/files/994570/75686_14_CH10_history_def_eng_vt.pdf